

Solid State Interaction Between Urea Nitrate and Phosphates of Iron and Aluminium

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Manuscript received 1 February 1978, revised 18 April 1978, accepted 10 May 1978

Urea nitrate is found to react with the phosphates of iron and aluminium in the solid phase. The interaction occurs on grinding urea nitrate with the tertiary phosphate of iron or aluminium together in a particular ratio for about an hour. The resulting product becomes completely water soluble when the mole ratio of the phosphate to urea nitrate is 1 : 2. The interaction occurs in two steps (i) formation of dibasic phosphate of iron or aluminium in the solid state and (ii) further protonation to soluble monobasic phosphate of iron or aluminium when placed in water in the presence of unreacted urea nitrate.

SOILS having lower pH contain higher amounts of aluminium, iron and reductant soluble phosphate.

The utilization of phosphorus by plants from these phosphates has been studied by a number of workers^{2,3}. Acid soils containing phosphates of iron and aluminium are "unavailable" to plants because these two elements are regarded as the main converters of "available" phosphate to "unavailable" phosphate¹. To make these phosphates available to plants especially in acid soils is therefore of considerable interest in soil chemistry. In the present investigation the author attempts to find out the solid state interaction between ferric and aluminium phosphates with urea nitrate on the lines earlier reported by the author for rock phosphates⁷. The work consists of grinding a fixed amount of ferric or aluminium phosphate with varying amounts of urea nitrate so as to determine the particular ratio of the phosphate to urea nitrate necessary for rendering it completely water soluble.

Experimental

Since the exact nature of iron and aluminium phosphates in soil is as yet unknown the experiments were carried out with laboratory reagent forms, $\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. Urea nitrate was prepared from urea and nitric acid⁴. It was purified by recrystallization. 1 g mole of ferric phosphate or aluminium phosphate was mixed with varying amounts of urea nitrate and ground in an agate mortar for about an hour under dry conditions.

To evaluate the extent of chemical reaction 1 g of the ground mixture was treated with absolute alcohol (in which all the reactants and products except the phosphates are soluble), filtered and in the filtrate the amount of iron nitrate or aluminium nitrate was estimated⁵. To determine the extent of

availability of phosphate 1 g of the resultant mixture was leached with 250 ml of water, filtered and the amount of P_2O_5 obtained in the filtrate was taken as water soluble phosphate. The amount of P_2O_5 soluble in 100 ml of 2% citric acid solution in the residue after leaching with water was taken as the citrate soluble phosphate⁶.

Results and Discussion

Ferric or aluminium phosphate was mixed with different amounts of urea nitrate and ground in an agate mortar for an hour under dry conditions. The amounts of water and citrate soluble P_2O_5 in such mixtures are presented in Table 1. With increasing

TABLE 1—WATER AND CITRATE SOLUBLE P_2O_5 IN UREA NITRATE-IRON/ALUMINIUM PHOSPHATE MIXTURES

Compound	Phosphate to urea-nitrate mole ratio	Total P_2O_5 %	Water soluble P_2O_5 %	Citrate soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of water soluble P_2O_5 %	Fraction of citrate soluble P_2O_5 %
$\text{FePO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1 : 0	42.04	—	—	—	—
	1 : 0.25	38.53	3.37	5.80	8.75	15.06
	1 : 0.50	35.55	6.58	10.76	18.50	30.27
	1 : 0.75	33.02	8.62	13.31	26.10	40.32
	1 : 1.00	30.82	11.11	18.52	36.04	69.10
	1 : 1.25	28.89	17.72	10.11	61.35	35.00
	1 : 1.50	27.19	20.38	6.54	74.94	24.06
	1 : 1.75	25.68	22.39	3.19	87.25	12.40
	1 : 2.00	24.32	24.30	—	99.90	—
	$\text{AlPO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	1 : 0	50.72	—	—	—
1 : 0.25		45.70	3.82	6.83	8.35	14.95
1 : 0.50		41.58	7.51	12.51	18.05	30.10
1 : 0.75		38.15	9.87	15.28	25.88	40.06
1 : 1.00		35.23	12.65	21.17	35.92	60.08
1 : 1.25		32.74	20.06	11.43	61.28	34.92
1 : 1.50		30.57	22.79	7.28	74.55	23.80
1 : 1.75		28.67	24.91	3.50	87.10	12.20
1 : 2.00		26.99	26.89	—	99.62	—

urea nitrate content, the percentage of water soluble phosphate increases and finally at the stage of 1 : 2

mole ratio cent per cent. water soluble mixtures are obtained. It has been observed that for both elements the mixture on treatment with water first forms a colloidal solution which on keeping for about 15 minutes forms a clear solution.

The conversion of the insoluble phosphates to the soluble form is due to protonation reactions which can take place either when the tertiary phosphate of iron or aluminium and urea nitrate are mixed or when the mixture is placed in water. In the former case ferric nitrate or aluminium nitrate is one of the products which is soluble in absolute alcohol (in which phosphates are insoluble). The nitrate of iron or aluminium formed when a fixed weight of the phosphate is mixed with increasing amount of urea nitrate is estimated and the results are shown in Table 2. The nitrate content in both

TABLE 2—IRON/ALUMINIUM NITRATE CONTENT IN ETHANOL EXTRACT

(1.87 g FePO₄·2H₂O/1.58 AlPO₄·2H₂O+CO(NH₂)₂·HNO₃)

Compound	Weight of urea nitrate (g)	Phosphate to urea nitrate mole ratio	Fe(NO ₃) ₃ /Al(NO ₃) ₃ Calculated (g)	Found (g)
FePO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.91	1 : 0.25	0.16	0.02
	0.62	1 : 0.50	0.32	0.08
	0.93	1 : 0.75	0.48	0.18
	1.23	1 : 1.00	0.65	0.32
	1.54	1 : 1.25	0.81	0.50
	1.85	1 : 1.50	0.97	0.73
	2.16	1 : 1.75	1.13	0.98
	2.46	1 : 2.00	1.29	1.23
	3.08	1 : 2.50	1.29	1.23
	3.69	1 : 3.00	1.29	1.23
AlPO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.91	1 : 0.25	0.14	0.02
	0.62	1 : 0.50	0.27	0.07
	0.93	1 : 0.75	0.41	0.15
	1.23	1 : 1.00	0.55	0.27
	1.54	1 : 1.25	0.69	0.43
	1.85	1 : 1.50	0.83	0.62
	2.16	1 : 1.75	0.97	0.83
	2.46	1 : 2.00	1.10	1.09
	3.08	1 : 2.50	1.10	1.09
	3.69	1 : 3.00	1.10	1.09

the cases increases with increasing amount of urea nitrate and reaches a limiting value when the mole ratio of the phosphate to urea nitrate is 1 : 2. Further increase in the urea nitrate content does not give rise to increased amount of the nitrate in the extract. The limiting value of the nitrate found corresponds to one mole of the phosphate mixed with two moles of urea nitrate.

Urea nitrate is an ionic salt while phosphates of iron or aluminium are basic and it seems from the above observation that on grinding the mixture an acid-base neutralization reaction occurs on account of an increase in the activation energy of the reaction—

The protonation reaction occurs in two steps. The first step is a solid-solid reaction whereas the second step is a solid-liquid reaction in which the nitric acid formed by the dissociation of urea nitrate reacts with the dibasic phosphate produced in the first step. This is supported by the fact that the ground mixture on treatment with water first forms a colloidal solution which on keeping for sometimes forms a clear solution.

Probably the reaction between urea nitrate and the tribasic phosphates of iron or aluminium takes place due to the mobility of hydrogen and nitrate ions. At the points of contact of the two solids, protonation of the phosphate occurs as a result of the movement of labile H⁺ ions from urea nitrate. The mobility of protons in urea nitrate crystals was established by Kuttly and Murthy⁵. This changes the electroneutrality of the tribasic phosphates of iron or aluminium and causes the displacement of Fe³⁺ or Al³⁺ ions which in turn combine with the nitrate present at the interphase resulting in the formation of iron or aluminium nitrate. These steps occurring at the phase boundary are followed by the bulk reaction, the rate of which varies depending upon the particle size of the reactants. The movement of nitrate ions from the bulk takes place due to the concentration gradient set up by the removal of nitrate ions at the surface. On grinding the textural and structural states of solids change and fresh surfaces of the reactants are exposed which enhances the rate of the chemical reaction.

It is well known that by treating an excess amount of tribasic phosphate with a less amount of aqueous acid one cannot produce only dibasic phosphate. A mixture of monobasic phosphate and dibasic phosphate is the eventual product. The experimental results in this investigation show that the protonation by urea nitrate follows a path other than that expected in an aqueous medium. This is supported by the fact that the monobasic phosphate of iron or aluminium is not produced in step (i). Had it been one of the products, the side reaction

would occur and urea phosphate CO(NH₂)₂·H₃PO₄ would have been the resulting product. Urea phosphate is soluble in absolute alcohol. Since no alcohol soluble phosphate is detected in the ground mixture of urea nitrate and tribasic phosphates of iron or aluminium the possibility of formation of monobasic phosphate is ruled out. This further supports the occurrence of step (i). The question

of the participation of water in reaction (i), as adsorbed or otherwise held at the surface is also eliminated by the formation of dibasic phosphate alone. Thus the step (i) is a solid-solid interaction and that the dibasic phosphate formed dissolves in excess of urea nitrate solution in the step (ii) to form monobasic phosphate rendering the whole mixture water soluble.

This investigation indicates that a ground mixture of urea nitrate and tertiary phosphates of iron or aluminium in the mole ratio of 2 : 1 may be used in acid soils as an excellent nitrophosphatic fertilizer. Moreover the insoluble iron and aluminium phosphates of acidic soils may be made available to plants by using urea nitrate.

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